

Chemical constituents of the bark of *Terminalia myriocarpa*

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β -Sitosterol, β -amyrin, oleanolic acid, betulinic acid, maslinic acid and arjunolic acid (2 α ,3 β ,24-trihydroxy-olean-12-en-28-
oic acid) have been isolated and characterized.

Terminalia myriocarpa Heureka and Muell-Arg. is a large evergreen tree which grows in the eastern Himalayan region of India, Nepal and Bhutan. Its bark extract is known to be used as a cardiac stimulant and also as a mild diuretic¹. The chemical constituents of the bark was investigated by two groups of workers. Barua *et al.*² isolated ellagic acid, gallic acid, chebalgic acid and chebulinic acid from the tannins of the bark and Singh *et al.*³ isolated β -sitosterol, fructose, 4,4'-5,5'-6,6'-hexahydroxy diphenic acid dilactone and calcium oxalate. The latter group of workers further reported that they could not isolate any triterpene from the bark of the said plant. Since many other plants belonging to the *Terminalia* family are known⁴⁻¹⁰ to contain a large variety of triterpenes and triterpene glycosides in quantity, the present investigation was undertaken to study the triterpene constituents of the bark of *T. myriocarpa* that resulted in isolation and characterization of β -sitosterol and five known triterpenes.

Results and discussion

Dried and powdered bark of *T. myriocarpa* was extracted successively with benzene and chloroform. The benzene extract was separated into neutral and acidic components. The neutral part on chromatography and crystallization yielded β -sitosterol and β -amyrin (1). The acidic component on esterification with diazomethane followed by chromatography and crystallization furnished methyl oleanolate (2), methyl betulinic acid (3) and methyl maslinic acid (4). Compounds 1-4 were identified by comparison with authentic samples. The chloroform extract was again separated into ether soluble acidic and neutral components. The neutral part did not yield any solid compound. The acidic component on esterification with diazomethane followed by usual

chromatography and crystallization yielded methyl maslinic acid (4) and methyl-2 α ,3 β ,24-trihydroxy-olean-12-en-28-oate or, methyl arjunolate (5). 5 on acetylation yielded methyl arjunolate triacetate (6). Both 5 and 6 were identified by comparing their physical and spectral data (¹H NMR and mass) with those available in the literature.

Experimental

The plant material was collected from Mungpoo (Darjeeling) during November 2002 and identified by Dr. G. G. Maity, Taxonomy Section, Department of Botany, University of Kalyani where a herbarium has been kept. All melting points reported are uncorrected. Homogeneity of compounds was checked by TLC on dried silica-gel plates and spots were visualized by iodine vapours. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra on Bruker-300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm). All solvents were purified, distilled and dried before use.

Air-dried and powdered bark (1.2 kg) of *T. myriocarpa* was extracted successively in a soxhlet apparatus with benzene and chloroform for 10 h. The benzene extract on evaporation of solvent yielded a greenish yellow gummy residue which was digested with ether and filtered. The ether insoluble amorphous residue was rejected. The ethereal solution was washed with a cold aq. NaOH (5%) solution (3 x 250 ml) and then with water until neutral. Evaporation of ether yielded the neutral ether soluble component as a greenish yellow gummy residue (5.1 g, Component-A). The combined alkali extracts of the ethereal solution was acidified with slow addition of conc. HCl to furnish a greenish white precipitate which was again taken in ether. The ethe-

real solution containing the acidic fraction was washed with water and esterified with an ethereal solution of CH_2N_2 . Usual work up afforded a yellow gummy substance (3.4 g, Component-B). The chloroform extract of the bark on evaporation of solvent also gave a brown gummy residue (8.5 g) which was again separated into ether soluble neutral and acidic fractions by the procedure described as before. The neutral part was obtained as a greenish yellow oil (1.2 g) that did not yield any solid substance on chromatography. The acidic fraction of the CHCl_3 extract on esterification with CH_2N_2 in ether followed by usual work up furnished a light yellow gummy residue (3.8 g, Component-C).

Examination of Component-A : β -sitosterol and β -amyryn (1) :

Repeated chromatography of Component-A over silica gel followed by crystallization yielded β -sitosterol (0.51 g), m.p. 134–135° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 134–137°) and β -amyryn (1, 0.8 g), m.p. 196–198° (lit.¹² m.p. 194–200°). Acetate of 1 prepared by usual procedure exhibited m.p. 236–238° (lit.¹² m.p. 237–242°). All the compounds were identical with authentic samples (by mixed m.p., Co-TLC and IR).

Examination of Component-B : methyl olenolate (2), methyl betulinate (3) and methyl maslinate (4) :

Component-B on repeated chromatography over columns of silica gel followed by crystallization yielded methyl oleanolate (2, 0.4 g, crystallized from CHCl_3 -acetone), m.p. 193–194° (lit.¹³ m.p. 194–196°), methyl betulinate (3, 0.15 g, crystallized from hot methanol), m.p. 220–222° (lit.¹³ m.p. 220–222°), and methyl maslinate (4, 0.54 g, crystallized from CHCl_3 -petroleum ether), m.p. 221–224° (lit.¹³ m.p. 227–228°) in benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) and benzene-ethylacetate (7 : 3) eluents respectively and were found to be identical with authentic samples (mixed m.p., Co-TLC and IR).

Examination of Component-C : methylmaslinate (3) and methylarjunolate (5)^{6,15} :

Chromatography of Component-C over a column of silica gel (100 g) yielded a solid (0.12 g) in benzene-ethylacetate (9 : 1) eluents and was identified as 3 as described above. Further elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (2 : 3) furnished an oily solid which on rechromatography followed by crystallization from hot methanol yielded colourless crystals of methylarjunolate (5, 0.76 g), m. p. 242–246° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 250–252°) (Found : C, 74.1; H, 10.14; M^+ 502. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 74.06; H, 10.03%; M^+ 502).

Acetylation of 5 : methyl arjunolate triacetate (6)^{16,17} :

Acetylation of 5 with acetic anhydride in pyridine followed by usual work up yielded 6 (0.42 g) as an amorphous solid and our attempts to crystallize it from various mixture of solvents were unsuccessful (Found : C, 70.78; H, 8.83; M^+ 628. $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 70.67; H, 8.98%; M^+ 628).

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